

Supplementary Figure 5. PW1/Sca-1 flow cytometric analysis of bulk, clonal, sub-clonal PICs. (A) Bulk expression of PW1 and Sca-1 at P3. (B) C9 clone expression of PW1 and Sca-1 at P2. (C) C9A sub-clone expression of PW1 and Sca-1 at P2. Plots are representative of bulk, n=1; clones, n=7; sub-clones, n=3.